

1 **Partial fusion of a cytochrome P450 system by carboxy-terminal**
2 **attachment of putidaredoxin reductase to P450cam (CYP101A1)**

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16 **Abstract**

17 Cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzymes catalyze the insertion of oxygen into carbon-
18 hydrogen bonds and have great potential for enzymatic synthesis. Application development
19 of class I CYPs is hampered by their dependence on two redox partners (a ferredoxin and
20 ferredoxin reductase), slowing catalysis compared to self-sufficient CYPs such as CYP102A1
21 (P450BM3). Previous attempts to address this have fused all three components in several
22 permutations and geometries, with much reduced activity compared to the native system. We
23 report here the new approach of fusing putidaredoxin reductase (PdR) to the carboxy-
24 terminus of CYP101A1 (P450cam) via a linker peptide and reconstituting camphor
25 hydroxylase activity with free putidaredoxin (Pdx). Initial purification of a P450cam-PdR
26 fusion yielded 2.0% heme incorporation. Co-expression of *E. coli* ferrochelatase, lengthening
27 the linker from 5 to 20 residues, and altering culture conditions for enzyme production
28 furnished 85% heme content. Fusion co-expression with Pdx gave a functional system with
29 comparable *in vivo* camphor oxidation activity as the native system. *In vitro*, the fused
30 system's steady state NADH oxidation rate was two-fold faster than that of the native system.
31 In contrast to the native system, NADH oxidation rates for the fusion enzyme showed non-
32 hyperbolic dependence on Pdx concentration, suggesting a role for the PdR domain; these
33 data were consistent with a kinetic model based on two-site binding of Pdx by P450cam-PdR
34 and inactive dimer formation of the fusion. P450cam-PdR is the first example of a class I
35 P450 fusion that exhibits significantly more favorable behavior than that of the native system.

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45 **Introduction**

46 The heme-dependent cytochrome P450 (CYP) superfamily of monooxygenases are found in
47 most domains of life,¹ from hepatocytes² and mitochondria,³ through plants,⁴ nematodes,⁵ and
48 bacteria,^{6, 7} to protozoa,^{8, 9} and viruses.¹⁰ Their varied provenances mirror their varied
49 functions; even within a particular species, several P450s with differentiated activities and
50 specificities can be found, testament to the biological importance of insertion of an oxygen
51 atom into a carbon-hydrogen bond, the fundamental reaction commonly catalyzed by these
52 enzymes.¹¹

53 CYP systems solve the problem of delivering the two necessary reducing equivalents
54 from NAD(P)H to the cytochrome synchronously with its hydroxylating catalytic cycle in
55 several ways.¹¹ *Eukaryota* employ several permutations of fused redox domains and *Bacteria*
56 and mitochondria often, but not exclusively, rely on shuttle ferredoxins to provide electrons.¹²
57 Bacterial class I CYP systems are commonly composed of an FAD-dependent ferredoxin
58 reductase, and a [2Fe-2S]-dependent ferredoxin, and the terminal P450 monooxygenase (Fig.
59 1A).¹³ Each of these components is usually highly specific, ensuring tight regulation of
60 electron transport and preventing cross talk between multiple systems in the same cell. The
61 three-component nature of these systems generates inherent kinetic impedance for substrate
62 oxidation when compared to one- (e.g. CYP102A1 (P450BM3) from *Bacillus megaterium*¹⁴)
63 or two-component CYP systems (e.g. vertebrate hepatic CYP3A4¹⁵) since electron transfer is
64 intermolecular rather than largely intramolecular. As a shuttle protein, the class I ferredoxins
65 must be able to recognize and bind both the ferredoxin reductase and CYP enzyme to give
66 [2Fe-2S]:heme or [2Fe-2S]:FAD orbital overlap for a physiologically appropriate rate of
67 electron transfer. Under physiological conditions, the first electron transfer to the ferric,
68 substrate-bound CYP from the reduced ferredoxin controls the NAD(P)H-oxidation and
69 substrate hydroxylation rates of class I systems.

70 The most studied class I cytochrome P450 is the camphor 5-hydroxylase P450cam
71 (CYP101A1) from *Pseudomonas putida*. P450cam and its cognate electron transfer
72 partners—the FAD-dependent putidaredoxin reductase (PdR) and the [2Fe-2S] putidaredoxin
73 (Pdx)—have been structurally characterized.¹⁶⁻²⁰ As a result of the extensive body of
74 biochemical and structural data, the P450cam system is considered the model of the bacterial
75 class I CYPs, despite its idiosyncrasies.²¹ This class contains a multitude of other CYPs with
76 potential for biotechnological applications but their kinetic properties inhibit widespread
77 development.²² Numerous CYPs are not genetically associated with their physiological
78 electron transfer partners, including those from metagenomic libraries. Activity reconstitution

79 relies on the opportune activity of known CYP-associated ferredoxins such as Pdx,^{23, 24} and
80 adrenodoxin (Adx) associated with the mitochondrial CYP11A1 (P450scc),²⁵⁻³⁰ amongst
81 others.³¹⁻³⁶ If these problems were resolved, processes could be facilitated in fields as diverse
82 as fine chemicals and pharmaceuticals,³⁷ e.g. *in vitro* synthesis of antibiotics by uncultivable
83 soil bacteria might become viable.^{38, 39}

84 Previous approaches have mimicked the naturally fused CYPs.^{40, 41} Every permutation
85 of a chain of P450cam, Pdx and PdR was constructed and expressed (Fig. 1B); all such
86 fusions showed slower *in vivo* camphor biotransformation than the native system.⁴² The
87 P450cam system components have been attached to a synthetic non-natural ternary linker;⁴³
88 in other work, they were fused to the subunits of proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA), a
89 hetero-trimer from *Sulfolobus solfataricus*, to form a self-assembling, branched super-
90 enzyme (Fig. 1C).^{44, 45, 46} These approaches illustrated the importance of flexibility in such
91 class I fusion systems to allow potentially orthogonal binding orientations between redox
92 partners for efficient electron shuttling by the ferredoxin. Class I CYPs have also been fused
93 to the carboxy-terminus of the reductase domain of P450Rhf from *Rhodococcus rhodochrous*
94 (Fig. 1D), but electron transfer rates were low.^{47, 48}

95 Since fusion of complete systems had seen limited success, we explored the creation
96 of fusions using only a subset of the P450cam system components, namely PdR and P450cam
97 (Fig. 1E), and investigated the electron transfer and camphor oxidation kinetics of the system
98 *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Partial fusion of CYP system enzymes has been reported: PdR was
99 chemically cross-linked to Pdx, which improved camphor hydroxylation kinetics at saturating
100 P450cam concentrations.⁴⁹ However, fusing of indirect redox partners has not been
101 described. After constructing a series of expression plasmids and optimizing conditions for
102 production of a maximally heme-incorporated P450cam-PdR fusion enzyme, we found that
103 this fused system oxidized DL-camphor identically to the native system *in vivo*. We
104 demonstrated enhanced electron transfer, and found that NADH oxidation *in vitro* showed
105 non-Michaelis-Menten dependence on Pdx concentration, which could be modeled by
106 considering an extended two-site sequential binding model that incorporates two distinct Pdx
107 binding sites and inactive dimerization of the fully Pdx-bound P450cam-PdR fusion.

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111 **Materials and methods**

112 ***Molecular biology***

113 Genes encoding P450cam and PdR had previously been cloned into expression plasmids.⁵⁰
114 The *camC* gene was amplified with primers incorporating NcoI and SacI restriction sites and
115 a sequence encoding a carboxy-terminal AAKKT linker (linker A, LA), while primers
116 incorporating SacI and HindIII sites were used to amplify *camA*. Amplified fragments were
117 assembled in the Multiple Cloning Site 1 (MCS1) of an NcoI/HindIII-linearized pRSFDuet-1
118 vector in a three-piece ligation step. This pRSFDuet::*camC-LA-camA* construct is referred to
119 as pFusion.

120 *E. coli* ferrochelatase, encoded by *hemH*, was amplified from genomic DNA, which
121 had been isolated using the Promega Genomic DNA Miniprep kit according to the
122 manufacturer's instructions. PCR primers incorporating NdeI and XhoI restriction sites
123 allowed ligation into the MCS2 of NdeI/XhoI-linearized pFusion to create the recombinant
124 plasmid pRSFDuet::*camC-LA-camA::hemH*, or pFusionH.

125 The original AAKKT linker in pFusionH was replaced with the sequence
126 DVSTEQSAKEAPAETLGAFR (linker 2, L2) by the MEGAprimer WHOLE Plasmid
127 (MEGAWHOP) method.^{51, 52} pFusionH was linearized by inverse PCR, which excluded the
128 linker region. Exactly complementary oligonucleotides containing the sequence encoding L2
129 and a *ca.* 10-nt 5'- and 3'-overlap with the linearized plasmid was synthesized (Eurofins
130 MWG Biotech, Germany) and used as a primer pair to amplify the linearized plasmid (Table
131 S1). After DpnI digest, the PCR product (a doubly-nicked plasmid) was then used to
132 transform *E. coli* DH5 α , from which the intact plasmid pRSFDuet::*camC-L2-camA*
133 (pFusionH2), was extracted and the insert sequences confirmed by Sanger sequencing
134 (Source Bioscience, UK).

135 ***Expression and purification of P450cam, Pdx, and PdR***

136 The *camC* gene encoding the non-dimerizing P450cam mutant C334A was used throughout,
137 and is referred to as the native enzyme.⁵³ Expression plasmids harboring the *camA*, *camB* and
138 *camC* genes, encoding the PdR, Pdx, and native P450cam enzymes, respectively, had
139 previously been constructed in our laboratory. The expression and purification of these
140 proteins have already been described.^{54, 55}

141 ***Expression and purification of fused P450cam-PdR enzymes***

142 A colony of *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) transformed with the appropriate pFusion plasmid and
143 grown on LB agar containing 30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ kanamycin (kan) was used to inoculate a starter
144 culture of TB containing 30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ kan (TB_{kan}). This culture was grown until OD₆₀₀ was

145 0.5–0.8 and used to inoculate a large-scale TB_{kan} culture at 2% v/v. The large culture was
146 grown at 37 °C and 200 rpm until OD₆₀₀ was 0.6–0.8. The temperature was then reduced to
147 20 °C, and shaking was reduced to 100 rpm. The culture was supplemented with 1 mM 5-
148 aminolevulinic acid (δ -ALA), 0.1 mM riboflavin, 4 mM ammonium ferric citrate (AFC), and
149 1 mM DL-camphor from a 100 mM stock in ethanol. After two hours, enzyme production
150 was induced with 40 μ M isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG).

151 Expression was continued for 72 h, or until the culture reached saturation (OD₆₀₀ \approx 8),
152 at which point the cells were harvested by centrifugation at 4000 \times g and 4 °C, before being
153 stored at –20 °C. To extract the fusion enzyme, cells were thawed at 4 °C and then
154 resuspended in 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, supplemented with 20% v/v glycerol, 1% v/v Triton
155 X-100, 1 mM DTT, 0.5% v/v β -mercaptoethanol (BME), 1 mM camphor, and 0.1 mg mL⁻¹
156 lysozyme from chicken egg white (Sigma-Aldrich, UK), ensuring cell wet weight was \leq 20%
157 w/v of the final suspension. This suspension was incubated at 4 °C for 2 h before cells were
158 lysed by sonication. Cell debris were removed by centrifugation at 39,000 \times g and 4 °C.

159 The cell-free lysate was loaded onto a 200 \times 50 mm DEAE-Sepharose (GE
160 Healthcare, UK) column and eluted with a gradient of 60–200 mM KCl (P450cam-LA-PdR),
161 or 80–230 mM KCl (P450cam-L2-PdR) in 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, supplemented with 1
162 mM camphor. Red-colored fractions were then concentrated by ultrafiltration and desalted on
163 a 500 mL bed-volume Sephadex G-25 (GE Healthcare, UK) column, which had been
164 equilibrated in 50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4.

165 Eluate from the G-25 column was concentrated by ultrafiltration and applied to a 120
166 \times 26 mm Source 15Q column (GE Healthcare), and eluted with a gradient of 50–700 mM
167 KCl (P450cam-LA-PdR) or 100–750 mM KCl (P450cam-L2-PdR) in 50 mM Tris-HCl, pH
168 7.4. The purest fractions, as indicated by $A_{420}/A_{280} \geq 1$, were pooled, concentrated to *ca.* 100
169 μ M, and filtered through a 0.22 μ m sterile syringe filter. Sterile glycerol was added to 50%
170 v/v for storage at –20 °C. Glycerol was removed immediately prior to experiments by gel
171 filtration on a PD-10 column (GE Healthcare, UK) equilibrated with 40 mM phosphate
172 buffer, pH 7.4. The P450 content was determined by the CO-difference spectrum method and
173 using $\epsilon_{450-490} = 91 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.^{56, 57}

174 ***Camphor-binding titrations***

175 All titrations were performed at 30 \pm 0.5 °C. P450cam or P450cam-L2-PdR was diluted to 2–
176 5 μ M using 40 mM phosphate, pH 7.4, in 2.5 ml, and 0.5–2 μ L of DL-camphor was added
177 using a Hamilton syringe from a 1, 10, or 100 mM stock solution in ethanol. After mixing,

178 the peak-to-trough absorbance difference, ΔA , was recorded on a Cary 50 spectrophotometer
179 between 700 nm and 250 nm. Further aliquots of camphor were added until ΔA did not
180 change further. The observed ΔA values were scaled for dilution, and the dissociation
181 constant, K_d , for camphor binding was obtained by fitting the scaled ΔA to the camphor
182 concentration using a rectangular hyperbola: $\Delta A = \Delta A_{\max} \times [\text{camphor}]/(K_d + [\text{camphor}])$. The
183 titrations were repeated with 200 mM KCl added from a 2 M stock solution in 40 mM
184 phosphate, pH 7.4 before the addition of camphor aliquots.

185 **Potassium-binding titrations**

186 Potassium binding titrations were carried out in 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.4, in 2.5 ml.
187 The P450cam-L2-PdR fusion was buffer exchanged to the Tris-HCl buffer by elution through
188 a PD-10 column. DL-Camphor was added as a 100 mM stock solution in ethanol to a final
189 concentration of 1 mM. Aliquots of a 2 M stock of KCl in 50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, were
190 added and the difference spectrum recorded until a final KCl concentration of 200 mM. The
191 peak-to-trough difference ΔA was scaled to account for dilution and the dissociation constant,
192 K_d , for potassium binding was determined by fitting the scaled ΔA values to KCl
193 concentration using a rectangular hyperbola: $\Delta A = \Delta A_{\max} \times [\text{KCl}]/(K_d + [\text{KCl}])$.

194 **Camphor biotransformation**

195 *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) cells were co-transformed with an appropriate pFusion plasmid and
196 pCW::*camB*, and an isolated colony from the LB_{amp/kan} agar plate was used to inoculate
197 LB_{amp/kan} medium. The culture was shaken overnight at 37 °C and 200 rpm, and then used to
198 inoculate a large-scale TB_{amp/kan} culture at 10% v/v. After 5 h at 37 °C and 200 rpm, 1 mM 5-
199 aminolevulinic acid (δ -ALA), 0.1 mM riboflavin, 4 mM and ammonium ferric citrate (AFC)
200 were added and the temperature was lowered to 30 °C. After one hour, 40 μ M IPTG was
201 added to induce expression of the camphor-oxidation system at 30 °C and 200 rpm for 16 h.

202 After centrifugation at $4000 \times g$ and 4 °C for 10 min, cell pellets were resuspended in
203 20% of their original culture volume in TB_{amp/kan} containing 1% w/v glucose. The P450
204 content was *ca.* 20 nM in both the fusion and native whole cell reactions after 24 h. The
205 culture was transferred to 2 L baffled flasks, with 200 mL culture per flask. DL-camphor was
206 added to 4 mM from a 100 mM stock in ethanol. Aliquots of 900 μ L samples of culture were
207 taken at several time points up to 24 h. 9-Hydroxyfluorene (75 μ M) was added as an internal
208 standard and the sample was extracted with 400 μ L ethyl acetate.⁵⁰ After phase separation by
209 centrifugation at $13,400 \times g$ for 1 min the organic phase was analyzed on a ThermoFinnegan
210 Trace GC instrument equipped with a flame ionization detector, an AutoSampler AS3000 and

211 a 30 m DB-1 fused silica column (0.32 mm diameter, 0.25 μm film thickness). The oven
212 temperature was held at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 min then increased to 220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ over 9 min, and held at 220
213 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min. Helium was used as the carrier gas. The 24 h extracts were also analyzed by
214 GC-MS to confirm product identities.

215 Serially diluting an aqueous indole (Sigma-Aldrich, UK) solution in volumetric flasks
216 generated a series of indole standards spanning 75 μM to 2.4 mM. Ethyl acetate extracts of
217 these standards were prepared as above; the resultant GC chromatograms were used to
218 calculate a standard curve of the detector response normalized to internal standard against
219 indole concentration.

220 *NADH turnover assays*

221 All turnover assays were carried out using a Cary 50 spectrophotometer at 30.0 ± 0.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a
222 1.2 mL solution of 40 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.4. Bovine liver catalase (100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was
223 added to all reactions containing DL-camphor. Mixtures were allowed to equilibrate for 2
224 min before reaction initiation.

225 Steady state NADH oxidation assays were performed in triplicate using 0.5 μM PdR,
226 5 μM Pdx, and 0.5 μM P450cam, or 5 μM Pdx and 0.5 μM P450cam-L2-PdR fusion. NADH
227 was added to *ca.* 320 μM to give $A_{340} = 2$. The reaction was initiated by adding 1 mM DL-
228 camphor from a 100 mM ethanol stock, and A_{340} was monitored. NADH oxidation rate was
229 calculated using $\epsilon_{340} = 6.22 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

230 Pdx titrations for NADH oxidation were performed in triplicate using 0.1 μM
231 P450cam with 0.5 μM PdR, or 0.1, 0.5, or 1.0 μM P450cam-L2-PdR fusion with and without
232 0.4 μM PdR. NADH was added as above. The reaction was initiated by adding 1 mM DL-
233 camphor from a 100 mM ethanol stock, and A_{340} was monitored. NADH oxidation rate was
234 calculated as above. Titrations against native P450cam produced a good non-linear least
235 squares fit to the Michaelis-Menten model; those against the fusion displayed non-Michaelis-
236 Menten behavior, and were initially analyzed by ordinary least squares fitting of the Hanes-
237 Woolf rearrangement of the Michaelis-Menten model: $[\text{Pdx}] / v = [\text{Pdx}] / k_{\text{cat}}[\text{Fus}] + K_m /$
238 $k_{\text{cat}}[\text{Fus}]$.

239 Ferricyanide was used as the terminal electron acceptor to measure NADH oxidation
240 by PdR or the PdR domain of the fused P450cam-L2-PdR enzyme. The reaction mixture
241 contained 10 nM PdR or P450cam-PdR. NADH was added as above. The reaction was
242 initiated by adding 1 mM $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$. A_{420} was monitored over time, and $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$
243 reduction rates were calculated using $\epsilon_{420} = 1.04 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

244 ***Spectral decomposition***

245 Samples of pure P450cam and PdR were used to generate UV-visible spectra standards,
246 which were used as a basis set for spectral decomposition of the UV-visible spectrum of the
247 P450cam-PdR fusions, allowing calculation of heme incorporation. Briefly, the spectrum of
248 the fusion protein was treated as a vector of absorbance values, for which the contribution
249 from P450cam and PdR was calculated by solving the system of linear equations in Eq. 1 to
250 find \mathbf{c} , where \mathbf{a} is a vector of length m corresponding to the absorbance measurements of the
251 fusion at m wavelengths, \mathbf{E} is a $2 \times m$ matrix containing the absorbances of the standards, and
252 \mathbf{c} is a vector of length 2 containing the relative contribution from each standard.

253
$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{c} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

254 Since \mathbf{E} is not a square matrix, this system cannot be solved using $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{E}^{-1}\mathbf{a}$. However, the
255 relation in Eq. 2 may be used. If the \mathbf{e}_{1j} are the P450cam absorbances and the \mathbf{e}_{2j} are the PdR
256 absorbances, then heme incorporation was calculated by $100 \times c_1/c_2$.

257
$$\mathbf{c} = (\mathbf{E}^T\mathbf{E})^{-1}\mathbf{E}^T\mathbf{a} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

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259

260 **Results and discussion**

261 ***Production and purification of fused P450cam-PdR***

262 Previous reports of CYP fusions suggested pivotal and unpredictable effects of both the
263 length and nature of the linker.^{42,43} The plasmid pRSFDuet-1, with two multiple cloning sites
264 (MCS) each downstream of a T7-promoter, was used for heterologous expression in *E. coli*.
265 The genes encoding PdR and P450cam-C334A were assembled with a five amino-acid linker
266 (LA, sequence AAKKT, Fig. 2A & 2B, Table S1) in MCS1 of pRSFDuet-1 to produce the
267 construct pRSFDuet::*camC-LA-camA* (pFusion, Fig. 2C). Previous studies had shown the
268 benefit of expressing hemoproteins in the presence of ferrochelatase (HemH).⁵⁸ The *E. coli*
269 *hemH* gene was amplified and cloned into MCS2 of pFusion to give the pFusionH construct
270 pRSFDuet::*camC-LA-camA::hemH*.

271 The linker AAKKT was chosen because previous work on the crystal structure of
272 fused CYP11A1 and Adx showed that it produced a good compromise between stability and
273 activity.⁵⁹ However, since the fusions in the present study were instead between CYP
274 (P450cam) and reductase (PdR) domains, a second linker was designed to mimic that found
275 in P450BM3, a natural fusion of a diflavin reductase domain and a CYP domain.¹⁴ This
276 linker (L2) had the sequence DVSTEQSAKEAPAETLGAFR and led to the construct
277 pRSFDuet::*camC-L2-camA::hemH* (pFusionH2, Fig. 2C).

278 After inducing P450cam-LA-PdR expression from pFusion, enzyme purification
279 followed the typical protocol for P450cam isolation.⁵⁴ Spectral decomposition of the UV-
280 visible spectrum of the product against P450cam and PdR standards indicated that the fusion
281 enzyme was severely heme-depleted, showing heme incorporation of 2.0% (Fig. 3A). To
282 improve heme incorporation, supplementation of the culture medium was explored (Table 1).
283 Initial supplementation with 100 μM δ -ALA, the committed heme precursor, and iron in the
284 form of 10 μM FeCl_2 , gave a modest increase in heme content to 5.8% (Fig. 3B). Increasing
285 the δ -ALA concentration to 500 μM raised the heme content to 26% while FeCl_2 at 50 μM
286 had a similar effect (6.9% heme content) as combining 100 μM δ -ALA with 10 μM FeCl_2 .
287 Addition of 1 mM DL-camphor on its own, without other supplements, resulted in much
288 higher heme incorporation (31%). On the other hand the presence of 2 mM Na_2EDTA
289 reduced heme assimilation to 8.6%. These observations indicated that higher heme flux from
290 supplementing with δ -ALA and FeCl_2 and stabilization of the P450cam fold by camphor
291 binding increased holoenzyme production, while binding of iron by EDTA^{4-} lowered the
292 heme flux and hence reduced the production of active enzyme. The pFusionH construct,

293 which co-expressed ferrochelatase, furnished a heme content of 22% in the presence of 100
294 μM δ -ALA, a significant improvement over the 5.8% heme content using pFusion.

295 Similar trends in heme content with culture conditions were observed with the fusion
296 containing the longer L2 linker (data not shown). A set of conditions for higher heme
297 incorporation into P450cam-PdR fusions was established as follows: the concentration of iron
298 in the culture medium during fusion expression was raised to 4 mM by using the non-toxic
299 soluble iron source ammonium ferric citrate (AFC), with 1 mM DL-camphor to stabilize the
300 P450cam structure, 1 mM of the heme precursor δ -ALA, 100 μM riboflavin to promote FAD
301 synthesis, and co-expression of HemH. Under these conditions the pFusionH2 construct
302 yielded the P450cam-L2-PdR fusion enzyme with 85% heme incorporation (Table 1, Fig.
303 3D). This enzyme was used for biochemical investigations.

304

305 ***In vivo activity of the P450cam-L2-PdR fusion***

306 The activity of the fused (P450cam-L2-PdR, Pdx) and native (P450cam, Pdx, PdR) systems
307 for whole-cell biotransformation of DL-camphor was compared over 24 h. *E. coli* BL21
308 (DE3) was transformed either with pFusionH2 and pCW::*camB*, or pRSFDuet::*camC*::*camA*
309 and pCW::*camB* plasmids and used for *in vivo* camphor oxidation. SDS-PAGE analysis
310 showed that pFusionH2-transformed cultures expressed a polypeptide at the expected size of
311 P450cam-L2-PdR, and that all enzymes necessary to reconstitute camphor 5-hydroxylase
312 activity were expressed (Fig. S1). Adjusted to the same P450 content, cultures expressing the
313 fusion enzyme oxidized DL-camphor at a similar rate to the native system (Fig. 4), with both
314 showing >99% camphor conversion after 1 hour. Interestingly, further oxidation of 5-*exo*-
315 hydroxycamphor to 5-oxo-camphor by the fusion enzyme was 39% lower than for the native
316 system.

317 GC-MS analysis identified indole in the culture supernatants (Fig. 4A & S2), with 4-
318 fold higher concentration in the reaction with the fusion compared to the native system.
319 When the cell growth and biotransformation were carried out in FB_{glycerol}, a minimal medium,
320 no indole was detected in either reaction (Fig. S3). It was not clear what caused these
321 differences.

322

323 ***In vitro activity of the P450cam-PdR fusion***

324 The CO-difference spectrum of purified P450cam-L2-PdR fusion enzyme showed the 450
325 nm Sorét band characteristic of the CYP superfamily (Fig. 5A) with a minor shoulder at 420
326 nm indicative of a small amount of misfolded hemoprotein.^{56, 60}

327 The electron transfer property of the PdR domain in the fusion was assessed by the
328 rate of ferricyanide reduction. For free PdR the rate of electron transfer from the reduced
329 FAD to the small molecule acceptor $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ is sufficiently fast to provide an indirect
330 measure of the rate of FAD reduction by NADH.^{12, 61, 62} The rate constants of FAD reduction
331 of native PdR ($1500 \pm 200 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and P450cam-L2-PdR ($1550 \pm 20 \text{ s}^{-1}$) were identical within
332 experimental error.

333 Substrate binding by native ferric P450cam is accompanied by conversion of the
334 heme from a low- to a high-spin state, as shown by the shift of the Sorét maximum from 419
335 nm to 390 nm. The fused system also exhibited this characteristic behavior (Fig. 5B & S4).
336 P450cam is also unusual in displaying cooperative camphor binding with potassium
337 binding.^{54, 63} The binding of potassium stabilizes an otherwise unfavorable conformation
338 around Tyr96 that orientates its phenol side chain into the substrate pocket where it forms a
339 hydrogen bond with the camphor carbonyl oxygen and tightens camphor binding. The K_d for
340 camphor binding by the P450cam-L2-PdR fusion in 40 mM phosphate buffer was $7 \pm 1 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$
341 (Fig. 5C), decreasing to $2.04 \pm 0.07 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ in the presence of 200 mM KCl. The K_d value for
342 native P450cam with 200 mM KCl was $1.2 \pm 0.1 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$. The K_d for potassium binding by the
343 fusion was $11.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ mM}$ (Fig. 5D), compared to $5.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ mM}$ for native P450cam.⁵⁴ These
344 data showed that the potassium binding site was intact in the fusion enzyme and there was
345 cooperative binding of potassium and camphor. However, the fusion of PdR appeared to
346 weaken both camphor and potassium binding, possibly also due to occlusion of the active site
347 or the potassium binding site by the PdR-domain.^{54, 64}

348 Next, the *in vitro* NADH oxidation activity of the reconstituted P450cam-L2-PdR
349 fusion with camphor as substrate was assayed and compared to the native system. When 5
350 μM Pdx is mixed with 0.5 μM P450cam-L2-PdR, or with 0.5 μM P450cam and 0.5 μM PdR,
351 the 10:1:1 Pdx:P450cam:PdR ratio results in the first electron transfer from reduced Pdx to
352 ferric P450cam being rate-determining. The NADH oxidation rates were 7.8 ± 0.3
353 $\text{nmol (nmol P450cam)}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $17.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ nmol (nmol P450cam-L2-PdR)}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Hence, the
354 fusion accepted electrons from reduced Pdx more than twice as quickly than in the native
355 system under these conditions. Such an improvement has not been reported for a fused
356 P450cam enzyme or any other fused class I CYP system. Previous fusions linked the entire

357 three-component system into a single polypeptide (Fig. 1B) but recent structural studies of
358 the Pdx:P450cam complex showed that orientation of the components is a crucial aspect of
359 efficient electron transfer.^{19, 65} The C-terminal Trp106 of Pdx is known from structural and
360 biochemical studies to be critical for the P450cam:Pdx interaction.⁶⁶ A C-terminal truncated
361 Adx is more efficient at transferring electrons to and hence reconstitute the activity of non-
362 native CYPs.^{25, 67, 68} Fusions must be flexible enough to enable the enzymes to adopt optimal
363 positions relative to each other. It can be envisioned that there might not be sufficient
364 flexibility in triple fusions for this to occur. With a P450cam-PdR fusion, Pdx would not be
365 constrained by fusion to another protein. Moreover, the proximity of PdR (from which Pdx
366 receives an electron) to P450cam (to which Pdx donates an electron) could lead to higher
367 turnover rates, i.e. a proximity effect. GC analysis of the products of camphor oxidation
368 catalyzed by the fusion enzyme *in vitro* (Fig. S5) showed >90 % coupling of NADH-derived
369 electrons to 5-*exo*-hydroxycamphor formation, a comparable value to that of the native
370 system.⁵⁴

371 Initial rates of NADH oxidation for the fused and native CYP enzymes were
372 measured in the presence of 1 mM DL-camphor and varying concentrations of Pdx to assess
373 the P450cam:Pdx interaction and electron transfer. For assays with native P450cam, an equal
374 concentration of PdR was also present. Under these conditions the first electron transfer from
375 Pdx^r to ferric P450cam is the slowest step,¹² and native P450cam showed single-site
376 Michaelis-Menten behavior with a k_{cat} of $64 \pm 3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Fig. 6A).⁶⁹ On the other hand, the
377 Hanes-Woolf plot of initial NADH oxidation rate by 0.1 μM P450cam-L2-PdR against Pdx
378 concentration showed significant deviation from linearity, in particular at low Pdx
379 concentrations where a distinct up-tick in $[\text{Pdx}]/v$ was observed (Fig. 6B). The apparent k_{cat}
380 was estimated to be 56.4 s^{-1} from a single-site fit. The kinetics with fusion concentrations of
381 0.5 and 1.0 μM showed more pronounced deviation from Michaelis-Menten kinetics, as well
382 as decreased apparent k_{cat} with increasing fusion enzyme concentration (estimated $k_{\text{cat}} = 46.2$
383 s^{-1} at 0.5 μM and 37.55 s^{-1} at 1.0 μM , Fig. 6B).

384 Since measurement of the Fdx^r-to-CYP electron transfer rate is usually carried out in
385 the presence of sufficient FdR to ensure that this step is rate determining,⁷⁰ initial NADH
386 oxidation rates were measured for 0.1 μM P450cam-L2-PdR, varying concentrations of Pdx,
387 and 0.4 μM PdR. Under these conditions, the Hanes-Woolf plots were also non-linear, but
388 with a distinct down-tick in $[\text{Pdx}]/v$ at low Pdx concentrations (Fig. 6C).

389

390 **Development of a kinetic model for fused P450cam-L2-PdR**

391 Increasing the fusion enzyme concentration increased the apparent cooperativity of the
392 enzyme-Pdx interaction while reducing the apparent k_{cat} , an unusual phenomenon. Since the
393 two Pdx-binding sites of the P450cam-PdR fusion were not equivalent, usual models (like the
394 Hill equation) of cooperative multi-site binding were, perhaps not surprisingly, inappropriate.
395 Instead, a derivative of the sequential-binding kinetic model was considered.^{71, 72} In this
396 model, substrate (Pdx in the present case) molecules may bind an enzyme in either a
397 particular sequence or randomly,⁷³ but only one or more of the complexes produce the
398 measured activity with independent rate constants $k_{\text{cat},i}$. Instantaneous equilibrium is a
399 simplifying assumption of this model. The observation that the native P450cam system
400 displayed Michaelis-Menten kinetics and that a mixture of 0.1 μM P450cam-PdR and 0.4 μM
401 PdR showed Michaelis-Menten kinetics at lower Pdx concentrations but more fusion-like
402 behavior at high Pdx concentrations led us to propose a model for the kinetics of the fusion
403 enzyme. The model (Fig. 7A) is based on several assumptions: (a) PdR reduction to PdR^r by
404 NADH is orders of magnitude faster than reduction of ferric camphor-bound P450cam by
405 Pdx^r, (b) reduction of oxidized Pdx (Pdx^o) to Pdx^r by PdR^r is fast under these conditions,¹² (c)
406 all P450cam domains are substrate-bound in the presence of 1 mM DL-camphor, and (d)
407 P450cam:Pdx^r binding occurs in preference to PdR:Pdx^r binding, since dissociation of newly-
408 reduced Pdx^r from PdR avoids product inhibition and allows the Pdx^r to interact with
409 P450cam as soon as possible.^{74, 75}

410 In this model the fused, camphor-bound ferric P450cam domain forms a complex
411 with Pdx^r with a dissociation constant K_{d1} . This complex can undergo electron transfer ($k_{\text{cat}1}$)
412 or the PdR domain can bind and reduce a Pdx^o molecule as a Pdx^r equivalent (K_{d2}), since
413 Pdx^o reduction is fast. The Pdx^r:Fus:Pdx^r complex can then either revert to Fus:Pdx^r, or
414 reduce the camphor-bound ferric P450cam domain ($k_{\text{cat}2}$). When free PdR is added to the
415 solution, this ternary complex becomes rare because free reductase competes for binding and
416 reduction of Pdx^o (K_{d4} , $k_{\text{cat}3}$). Finally, the lowering of k_{cat} with increasing fusion enzyme
417 concentration suggested the formation of an inactive dimeric form. This possibility is taken
418 into account by an equilibrium between the ternary Pdx^r:Fus:Pdx^r complex with another
419 fusion enzyme molecule to form a catalytically inactive quaternary complex (K_{d3}), although
420 other dimerization mechanisms may exist. Based on this model, the initial rate of NADH
421 oxidation is given by Eq. 3:

422

423
$$-\frac{d[\text{NADH}]}{dt} = [\text{Fus}] \frac{k_{\text{cat}1} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]}{K_{\text{d}1}} + k_{\text{cat}2} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2}{K_{\text{d}1}K_{\text{d}2}} + k_{\text{cat}3} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{PdR}]}{K_{\text{d}1}K_{\text{d}2}K_{\text{d}4}}}{1 + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]}{K_{\text{d}1}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2}{K_{\text{d}1}K_{\text{d}2}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{Fus}]}{K_{\text{d}1}K_{\text{d}2}K_{\text{d}3}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{PdR}]}{K_{\text{d}1}K_{\text{d}2}K_{\text{d}4}}}$$
 Eq. 3

424

425 where the $K_{\text{d},i}$ are the dissociation constants and the $k_{\text{cat},j}$ are the rate constants for electron
426 transfer for the complexes in Fig. 7A.

427 In order to avoid over-fitting and over-parameterization, initial fitting to Eq. 3 varied
428 only terms containing $K_{\text{d}1}$, $K_{\text{d}2}$, $K_{\text{d}3}$, $k_{\text{cat}1}$, and $k_{\text{cat}2}$ using the data collected in the absence of
429 free PdR (Fig. 8A). The remaining parameters $K_{\text{d}4}$ and $k_{\text{cat}3}$ were then fit to all the data while
430 holding the other parameters fixed (Fig. 8B). This approach produced a reasonable fit for
431 most of the data although there were some residual deviations at low Pdx concentration.

432 The fitted values show that binding of the first Pdx molecule by the fusion enzyme is
433 weaker than for the native system ($K_{\text{d}1} = 17 \pm 2 \mu\text{M}$ compared to $K_{\text{m}} = 7.0 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{M}$),
434 possibly because the PdR domain occludes the Pdx binding site in the fusion. In light of
435 weaker camphor and potassium binding observed for the P450cam domain of the fusion
436 compared to the native enzyme, weaker Pdx^{r} binding is not surprising. The fitted value for
437 $k_{\text{cat}1}$ was $53 \pm 7 \text{ s}^{-1}$, close to the value of $64 \pm 3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for k_{cat} , the corresponding parameter for
438 the Michaelis-Menten model of Pdx^{r} binding and oxidation by native P450cam.

439 The dissociation constant of the second Pdx binding event ($K_{\text{d}2} = 8 \pm 2 \mu\text{M}$) is smaller
440 than the first, and identical within experimental error to the native system's K_{m} (Fig. 8A).
441 Multi-site enzymes often display cooperativity, a phenomenon where successive binding
442 events become increasingly thermodynamically favorable, due to conformational changes in
443 the protein.⁷⁶ Since the P450cam-PdR fusion is an artificial enzyme, it might not be expected
444 that such an effect would be observed. However, the second Pdx^{r} binding event may occur
445 through several mechanisms, including nascent Pdx^{r} moving from the fused PdR domain, or
446 by Pdx^{r} from bulk solution interacting with the P450cam domain. Therefore, the decrease in
447 $K_{\text{d}2}$ compared to $K_{\text{d}1}$ could be attributed to a proximity effect arising from fusion of the Pdx-
448 reducing PdR domain to P450cam.

449 Pdx^{r} oxidation by the ternary complex ($k_{\text{cat}2} = 42 \pm 2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is marginally slower than by
450 the binary complex ($k_{\text{cat}1} = 53 \pm 7 \text{ s}^{-1}$). It is possible that the contribution to $K_{\text{d}2}$ from rapid
451 Pdx^{o} recruitment and reduction to Pdx^{r} —which then could switch to the adjacent P450cam
452 domain—by the PdR domain, while it manifests as tighter binding ($K_{\text{d}2}$), is a multi-step

453 process which is slower than simple Pdx^f oxidation by the P450cam domain, represented by
454 k_{cat1} .

455 The catalytically inactive complex of two fusion enzyme molecules and two Pdx
456 molecules could explain, in terms of self-inhibition, the empirical decrease in apparent k'_{cat} as
457 fused P450cam-PdR enzyme concentration increased (Fig. 6B), in contrast to native P450cam
458 under similar conditions (Fig. 6A). The observed data provide no insight into the structure of
459 the [Fus:Pdx^f]₂ dimer (Fig. 7A), although it may be envisioned as a homo-dimer of Fus:Pdx^f
460 hetero-dimers. The relatively small dissociation constant for this complex ($K_{d3} = 1.8 \pm 0.2$
461 μM) may reflect an increase in the interfacial binding area in comparison to a single Fus:Pdx^f
462 interaction.

463 The proposed model also suggests how the addition of free PdR dampens the
464 sigmoidal NADH oxidation kinetics of the fused system by competing with the PdR domain
465 in the fusion enzyme for Pdx molecules. The affinity of PdR for Pdx ($K_{d4} = 0.03 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{M}$,
466 Fig. 8B) is shown to be two orders of magnitude higher than that of P450cam ($7.0 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{M}$,
467 Fig. 6A); such an extreme difference has been seen previously by calorimetry.⁷⁷ This
468 proposed model therefore explains the non-linearity of the PdR-supplemented fusion
469 system's hybrid NADH oxidation kinetics (Fig. 6C): at low Pdx concentrations, the
470 proximity effect of the fused PdR domain is removed because Pdx^o binds preferentially to the
471 free, excess PdR. At higher Pdx concentrations, Pdx^o binding with the fused PdR is more
472 likely, especially as the native PdR becomes saturated, so the proximity effect (with its
473 attendant potential for inactive dimer formation) is more prevalent.

474

475 **Conclusion**

476 Protein recognition and electron transfer between enzymes in class I CYP systems is still not
477 fully understood.³² Slow kinetics have constrained development of these technologically
478 promising enzymes for applications.⁷⁸ We have shown that partial fusion of a class I CYP
479 system can lend it favorable properties. Changes in the linker peptide and addition of
480 common culture supplements enabled the production of the almost fully heme-incorporated
481 CYP-FdR fusion. This system is catalytically active *in vivo* and *in vitro*. In addition to the
482 convenience of such a fusion, the unusual kinetic properties allowed the construction of a
483 reasonable model of binding events. This model may allow future improvements to the fused
484 enzyme, and also facilitate better understanding of ferredoxin-to-CYP electron transfer. As
485 such, partially fused class I CYP systems merit further investigation. Finally, given that PdR
486 can show high activity for the reduction of non-native electron transfer ferredoxins from

487 other CYP systems, such as Arx from *Novosphingobium aromaticivorans* and Pux from
488 *Rhodopseudomonas palustris*,^{79, 80} fusions of CYP enzymes with PdR could be tested for
489 activity reconstitution with native forms as well as engineered variants of these ferredoxins.

490

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Table 1. Summary of heterologous expression conditions for P450cam-PdR fusion constructs and the resultant heme incorporation of the isolated enzyme as calculated by spectral decomposition of its electronic spectrum (see Materials & Methods). δ -ALA: 5-aminolevulinic acid, AFC: ammonium ferric citrate, RF: riboflavin, Camphor: DL-camphor, HemH: co-expression of *E. coli* ferrochelatase.

δ -ALA (μ M)	FeCl ₂ (μ M)	AFC (mM)	RF (μ M)	EDTA (mM)	Camphor (mM)	HemH	Linker	Heme (%)
–	–	–	–	–	–	–	LA	2.0
100	10	–	–	–	–	–	LA	5.8
500	–	–	–	–	–	–	LA	26
–	50	–	–	–	–	–	LA	6.9
500	50	–	–	–	–	–	LA	40
–	–	–	–	–	1	–	LA	31
–	–	–	–	2	1	–	LA	8.6
100	–	–	–	–	–	Yes	LA	22
1000	–	4	100	–	1	Yes	L2	85

Fig. 1. Electron-transfer in wild type and artificially fused class I CYP systems. (A) After NADH oxidation by the ferredoxin reductase (FdR) electrons are shuttled singly by a ferredoxin (Fdx) to the cytochrome P450 (CYP) to catalyze oxygen insertion into a C–H bond. Since this is a relatively slow, intermolecular process, attempts have been made to fuse the three component proteins into a single polypeptide to improve kinetics.¹¹ (B) Linear fusion of the P450cam system from *Pseudomonas putida* caused a reduction in camphor hydroxylation rate *in vivo*.⁴² (C) Fusion of the P450cam system to PCNA, a self-assembling hetero-trimer.⁴⁴ (D) The reductase of the P450Rhf system from *Rhodococcus rhodocrous* has been systematically fused to a panel of class I P450s, reconstituting the activity of some of them.⁴⁷ (E) The present work describes a partially fused P450cam system, with the amino-terminus of PdR connected to the carboxy-terminus of P450cam by a peptide linker, leaving Pdx free to shuttle electrons between the two domains.

Fig. 2. Design and construction of fused P450cam-PdR constructs. The plasmids for P450cam-PdR expression went through three generations of construction. (A) The P450cam and PdR domains were to be linked by a peptide chain connecting the P450cam carboxy-terminus to the PdR amino-terminus. The linker would be encoded in an artificial fused gene. (B) Two linkers were used. The first (LA) was based on work that fused P450scc (CYP11A1) and Adx for crystallization of the enzyme complex, where the AAKKT linker produced a functional fusion protein.⁵⁹ The second (L2) contained 20 amino acid residues and was based on the linker found in naturally fused P450BM3 (CYP102A1) from *Bacillus megaterium*. Both linkers were extended due to the incorporation of a *SacI* restriction site. (C) The plasmid pFusion, derived from pRSFDuet-1, was converted to pFusionH by insertion of the *E. coli* ferrochelatase gene (*hemH*) into the second multiple cloning site (MCS2). The third generation plasmid, pFusionH2, was constructed by swapping linker LA for linker L2 using inverse PCR and MEGAWHOP.

Fig. 3. Optimization of heme incorporation in fused P450cam-PdR. Heterologous expression conditions and inter-domain linker length were varied to increase heme incorporation of the P450cam-PdR fusion. (A-D) Heme incorporation for fusion enzymes prepared under several conditions was calculated by spectral decomposition of the electronic spectrum of the purified fusion enzyme based on the spectra of purified native P450cam and PdR. AFC: ammonium ferric citrate.

Fig. 4. *In vivo* activity of the fused P450cam-PdR system in TB medium. To test the camphor 5-hydroxylase activity of the fused P450cam-PdR system in the presence of Pdx, *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) were transformed with pFusionH2 or pRSFDuet::*camA*::*camC* and pUC18::*camB* and induced in TB, a rich medium, in the presence of 40 μM IPTG and 1 mM DL-camphor. GC analysis was performed on ethyl acetate extracts of culture supernatant (three biological replicates) at several time points until 24 h. (A) Typical GC analysis for culture supernatant from the fused system after 0 and 24 h incubation. (B) The abundance of DL-camphor, 5-*exo*-hydroxycamphor, 5-*oxo*-camphor, and indole were followed over time. FID = Flame ionization detector.

Fig. 5. Substrate binding of the fused P450cam-PdR enzyme. (A) Reduced, CO-bound P450cam-PdR fusion has a prominent 450 nm Sorét band, characteristic of the CYP superfamily; the shoulder at 420 nm can be seen, indicative of the inactive P420 form. (B) The Sorét band of ferric P450cam-L2-PdR at 419 nm shifted increasingly to 390 nm with DL-camphor concentration. (C) The maximal Sorét band shift for fused P450cam-PdR was lower than for native P450cam, and the calculated K_d was two-fold higher in high potassium solution. Lowering the potassium concentration reduced the camphor K_d for the fusion, mimicking the behavior seen previously in P450cam. (D) Fused P450cam-PdR also had a two-fold higher dissociation constant, K_d , for potassium ion binding in the presence of excess DL-camphor.

Fig. 6. NADH oxidation kinetics of the reconstituted P450cam-L2-PdR fusion. NADH oxidation by fused P450cam-PdR in the presence of Pdx was measured and compared to the native system. (A) The native P450cam system shows Michaelis-Menten kinetics. (B) Hanes-Woolf plots showing the non-Michaelis-Menten behavior of the P450cam-L2-PdR fusion: low Pdx concentrations give a deviation from linearity, and best-fit k_{cat} , k'_{cat} , decreases as fusion concentration increases. Doping the system with PdR has similar but less pronounced behavior. (C) An equimolar amount of PdR was added to 0.5 μM P450cam-PdR and Pdx was titrated across a similar concentration range. The kinetic behavior was different, with lower K_m and k_{cat} values.

B

$$-\frac{d[\text{NADH}]}{dt} = v = [\text{Fus}] \cdot \frac{k_{\text{cat}1} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]}{K_{d1}} + k_{\text{cat}2} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2}{K_{d1}K_{d2}} + k_{\text{cat}3} \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{Fus}]}{K_{d1}K_{d2}K_{d3}}}{1 + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]}{K_{d1}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2}{K_{d1}K_{d2}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{Fus}]}{K_{d1}K_{d2}K_{d3}} + \frac{[\text{Pdx}]^2[\text{PdR}]}{K_{d1}K_{d2}K_{d4}}}$$

Fig. 7. A proposed model for NADH oxidation kinetics of the reconstituted P450cam-L2-PdR fusion. (A) Pdx^r-to-P450cam electron transfer is the rate-limiting step of NADH oxidation. The native system conforms to the Michaelis-Menten model (green pathway). However, the P450cam-L2-PdR fusion deviates strongly from Michaelis-Menten behavior. An extended two-site sequential-binding model (green and black pathways) was proposed to explain the observed kinetics of the fused system. (B) Based on the proposed kinetic model, a function describing the initial rate of NADH oxidation in terms of enzyme concentrations could be derived, assuming instantaneous equilibrium.

Fig. 8. Best fit of the proposed kinetic model to the observed data. (A–B) The model appears to explain the decrease in observed k_{cat} with increasing fusion concentration, along with apparent cooperativity at low Pdx concentrations. In addition, it explains the fused-native hybrid kinetics seen when the fusion was assayed in the presence of free PdR.